

Response letter to Fernandez-Guerra biorxiv commentary on Rodríguez del Río et al 2022
(<http://disq.us/p/2n9a30u>)

Dear Antonio Fernández-Guerra,

We have read your comment with interest and surprise, as we always recognised your preprint paper openly, citing Vanni et al. (2020) in our manuscript and even referring to it as a foundational study in the field. We understand that we work on a similar topic and use similar methods and terminology but, as we hope to clarify here*, our data, analyses and biological findings are conceptually and technically different from those presented in Vanni et al.

In any case, we took your letter as constructively as possible and we would be happy to include our analyses and comparisons as additional references and supplementary materials in upcoming revisions of our manuscript, as we are confident that both studies do not overlap as expressed in your comments.

** The content of our response letter was shared, reviewed and agreed by the authors of Vanni et al. prior to publication.*

Summary:

1. **Rodríguez del Río et al, *does cite* Vanni et al.**, as well as other relevant methodological advances developed by their co-authors, such as MMSeqs2 and Linclust, explicitly acknowledging them **as a foundational work** and therefore allowing any interested reader to trace the origin of novel ideas.
2. Rodríguez et al. and Vanni et al. have a **completely different focus**.
 - a. Vanni et al. focused on developing a methodology for unifying known and unknown protein families. They demonstrated how this strategy can reduce the number of unknowns in metagenomics datasets, and analyzed the diversity and lineage-specificity of functionally unknown protein clusters vs the known ones using metagenomic and genomic gene catalogs. *Focus: **novel methods and known vs unknown comparisons***.
 - b. Rodríguez del Río et al. focused on characterizing a subset of high-quality predictions of unknown protein families that are unique from uncultivated lineages, non-orphan and under strong selection; further delineating novel protein families that i) co-occur in the same genome of species from particular lineages, ii) are potentially associated with specific metabolic pathways or iii) represent putative synapomorphic traits for high-rank uncultivated lineages. *Focus: **characterizing the unique genetic repertory of uncultivated taxa***.
3. All findings in Rodríguez del Río et al. refer to a **conceptually different set of data** as compared to Vanni et al.
 - a. In Vanni et al. most analyses refer to a generic classification of protein families into functionally known versus unknown, without distinguishing between those present in cultured and uncultured species, nor discarding orphan genes (e.g. ~60% of their lineage-specific clusters are species-specific).
 - b. In Rodríguez del Río et al., all results and biological interpretations refer to a subset of protein families within the unknown category that are exclusive from

uncultivated organisms, not orphan, and having particular genomic properties (e.g. under strong purifying selection). No results are reported that refer to comparisons between known and unknown protein families, and **no results can be extrapolated to the general pool of unknowns**.

4. **Rodríguez del Río et al. focused on maximizing the quality of predictions**, while Vanni et al. used a comprehensive approach.

- a. The unknown protein families predicted in Rodríguez del Río et al. were inferred based on mostly full-length genes that span more than one species, contain a conserved region of at least 20aa, have expression data/predictions, are under purifying selection, have no obvious homologs in cultured species, and have a reference genome to infer reliable taxonomic annotations and genomic contexts. As a result, all protein clusters with detectable homologs in cultured species and the vast majority of the unknowns were discarded and not included in subsequent analyses.
- b. Vanni et al. used a comprehensive approach for most of their biological analyses, using a set of clusters that might be over-split, due to the large number of fragmented genes present in metagenomics (as recognised in their own paper) and orphan genes (i.e. no homologs beyond species level).

5. Major findings in **Rodríguez del Río et al. are novel and do not overlap** with the observations in Vanni et al.

- a. Rodríguez del Río et al. reconstructed the genomic context and **calculated synteny conservation** for over 400k unknown protein families, delineating particular cases embedded in highly conserved **functional contexts associated with key metabolic processes**. In Vanni et al., genomic context conservation is shallowly showcased as an example of the potential of their approach.
- b. Rodríguez del Río et al., identified uncultivated lineages where **individual organisms contain a striking number of the selected *subset* of unknown protein families** from their catalog (i.e. high-quality, uncultivated-only, not-orphan novel fams per genome), linking them to potential functional roles; which does not compare with the observations reported in Vanni et al. By contrast, and although the data sets used are not equivalent, results in Rodríguez del Río et al. would largely contradict the main observation made in Vanni et al. about the Patescibacteria phylum having the greatest content of unknowns (see section 3).
- c. Rodríguez del Río et al. predicted over 900 novel protein families as putative synapomorphic traits for high-rank uncultivated lineages. This is, novel traits that are both highly specific and prevalent for all organisms under a given lineage. In their letter, **Vanni et al. confronted their lineage-specificity (LS) results with our synapomorphic predictions, which are not comparable**. As we show in section 4 of this report, the LS results shown by Vanni et al. would be incorrect if interpreted as synapomorphies. Most importantly, **Vanni et al never discussed any protein family that could potentially represent a synapomorphic trait at basal taxonomic levels**, and only brought this claim in their letter.
- d. Rodríguez del Río et al. reported putative synapomorphic protein families at high-rank levels **as traits of great evolutionary significance**, showing that they are also under **stronger selective pressures than other unknown families**. The results in Vanni et al. do not compare conceptually or technically with any of those findings: they report that functionally unknown protein families are more phylogenetically conserved than the known ones, which addresses a different

- question, performs a different comparison and uses a different metric than in Rodríguez del Río et al. (see section 5 for additional data).
- e. The subset of unknown protein families predicted in **Rodríguez del Río et al. inverts the ecological patterns observed in Vanni et al. and Coelho et al.** (see section 6)
 - i. Vanni et al. reported functionally unknown genes to be ecologically narrow, acknowledging the existence of a small fraction of broadly distributed families in all the protein family categories (known and unknown).
 - ii. Rodríguez del Río et al. demonstrate that the subset of predictions delineated with their analyses are largely widespread across samples and biomes, and most are not associated with mobile elements.
 - f. Rodríguez del Río et al. make available an online resource to graphically explore and interpret their predictions (<https://novelfam.cgmlab.org>), which is largely different both in content and form from the AGNOSTOS database released in Vanni et al. (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12459056>).

6. The methods used in Rodríguez del Río et al. are standard in the field, already published, and properly cited. (see section 8)

- a. The methodology used to identify novel gene families does not follow the approach presented in Vanni et al, but the one published by us and colleagues in Salazar et al, 2019. In such work, published prior to Vanni et al., we already described a method to unify known and unknown protein families using genomic and metagenomic data, which we also used to predict putative functions of unknown metagenomic protein families based on co-expression analyses.
- b. Rodríguez del Río et al. used AntiFam to locate spurious sequences, which is a generic procedure. We don't think this should be taken as a lack of recognition to Vanni et al.
- c. Rodríguez del Río et al. mapped their predictions to the most relevant catalog of unknown, but putatively functional, small peptides (Sberro et al. 2019); which is properly cited. We don't think this should be taken as a lack of recognition to Vanni et al.
- d. Rodríguez del Río et al mapped all their predictions to Price et al. to provide further hints on their putative functional roles. Vanni et al. used one example from Price et al. to showcase the use of genomic context for functional analyses. We don't know how our use of Price et al. could mean a lack of recognition to Vanni et al.
- e. Rodríguez del Río et al. developed their own ad hoc method to identify and date synapomorphic traits at high-rank levels, which is, as we show in section 4, conceptually different from the method used in Vanni et al.

Jaime Huerta Cepas and Álvaro Rodríguez del Río

Technical and scientific analysis

Point-by-point response

1. On the supposed omission of recognition

*"While we commend their efforts to unify known and unknown gene families and generate community resources such as <https://novelfams.cgmlab.org/>, we regretfully report that the manuscript by Rodríguez del Río et al. **fails to acknowledge extensive previous work** on this topic such as FUnkFams by Wyman et al. [1], and our recent study by Vanni et al. [2], which has made available a similar resource, AGNOSTOS-DB [3]." (Fernandez-Guerra, bioRxiv commentary) Even though studies mentioned here have already reported many of the major findings reported in Rodríguez del Río et al. the current manuscript does not cite FUnkFams, and cites Vanni et al. only once from the Introduction, without highlighting significant parallels between the approaches and findings of the two studies, which we find unfortunate.*

By this opening paragraph, Vanni et al. create the false impression that their paper was not cited in Rodríguez del Río et al., (2022).

However, **we did cite** (Vanni et al., 2020), as well as other relevant methodological advances developed by their co-authors, such as MMSeqs2 and Linclust. In fact, we recognised these papers not only as an important contribution to unifying the known and unknown sequence space, but **also as the foundational work that enabled our study**, dedicating a full paragraph to acknowledge it:

*"Secondly, it is now possible to use sensitive homology sequence searches and clustering algorithms on huge genomic catalogs 17,18 (**MMSeqs2, Linclust**). This has allowed recent metagenomic surveys to employ the concept of protein families — rather than individual gene entries¹⁹ — **to identify and quantify genetic novelty** 15,20 (**Vanni et al, 2020**), contributing to the annotation of distant homologs and reducing the number of putative orphan genes. **Most importantly, these advances have laid the foundation** for the systematic analysis of thousands of uncultured organisms under a common phylogenomic framework, which allowed us to address long-standing questions on the extent and biological value of their seemingly unrelated orphan genes" (Rodríguez del Río et al. 2022)*

In fact, contrary to ignoring the manuscript by Vanni et al., we followed with great interest the six preprint versions posted in biorxiv since 2020, making sure that our findings were built upon them (as expressed in the above paragraph) and not overlapping with their observations (as hopefully clarified in this response).

For instance, our analyses addressed many of the challenges that Vanni et al. let open in their closing remarks:

"(...) But severe challenges remain, such as the dependence on the quality of the assemblies and their gene predictions, as shown by the analysis of the ribosomal protein GCCs where many of the recovered genes are incomplete." (Vanni et al 2020)

Indeed, due to the large environmental fraction of Vanni et al. dataset, more than 50% of their genes are not full-length, and only 20% of the non-discarded clusters (4% over total) were considered high-quality.

By contrast, we based our work on more than 140,000 medium and high-quality MAGs and SAGs unified from different sources and environments, where almost all genes are predicted as complete and they all have a reference genome.

“(.) In any case, we still face the challenge of discriminating between genuine and artifactual singletons (Höps et al., 2018). There are currently no methods available to provide a plausible solution and, at the same time, being scalable.” (Vanni et al 2020)

To circumvent this problem, Vanni et al. excluded technical singletons and small clusters from their dataset and further analyses. However, they didn't address the fact that most of their protein families (e.g., ~60% of their lineage-specific clusters) are still orphan genes at the species level, as they lack homologs beyond the same species.

In our study, we used phylogenomics to locate and analyze unknown protein families that span at least 2 species (not orphan) and that are particularly relevant from a functional and evolutionary perspective (e.g. by synteny conservation, selective pressure, etc), which excluded the vast majority of the protein clusters inferred, even when they were technically correct.

“(.) our work lays the foundations for further developments of clear guidelines and protocols to define the different levels of unknown (Thomas and Segata, 2019) and should encourage the scientific community for a collaborative effort to tackle this challenge.” (Vanni et al 2020)

Indeed, in Vanni et al. all findings refer to the global category of functionally unknown genes versus the known ones (without distinguishing between cultured vs uncultured species, nor assessing their potential functional significance).

In our study, all results and biological interpretations refer to a small fraction of protein families within the unknown category (those specific from uncultivated taxa), which were also heavily biased towards certain genomic properties and thresholds, with the aim of maximizing the quality and value of our predictions. Therefore, none of our results can be extrapolated to the whole unknown sequence space, invalidating any direct comparison with more comprehensive approaches like in Vanni et al.

In their comment, Vanni et al. also refer to their follow up preprint paper AGNOSTOS-DB (Vanni et al., 2021), as well as FunkFams, by (Wyman et al., 2018). However, FunkFams refers to a dataset and scope that are very different from Rodríguez del Río et al.: e.g., they looked for unknown families derived from sequenced genomes at JGI and mapped then to metagenomics data, which is the opposite of what we do (predicting families that are only found in environmental samples). Similarly, we think that the resource AGNOSTOS-DB (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12459056>) does not compare in form or content to the online graphical explorer of predictions that Rodríguez del Río et al. made available at <https://novelfams.cgmlab.org>.

2. Conceptual differences between Rodríguez del Río et al. and Vanni et al.

“Even though studies mentioned here have already reported many of the major findings reported in Rodríguez del Río et al., the current manuscript does not cite FUnkFams, and cites Vanni et al. only once from the Introduction, without highlighting significant parallels between the approaches and findings of the two studies, which we find unfortunate.” (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

As we hope to clarify in the following sections, we think that the focus and therefore major findings in both studies do not overlap.

Rodríguez del Río et al focused on characterizing a subset of high-quality predictions of unknown protein families that are unique from uncultivated lineages, non-orphan and under strong selection; further delineating novel protein families that co-occur in the same genome of species from particular lineages, are potentially associated with specific metabolic pathways and/or representing putative synapomorphic traits for high-rank uncultivated lineages. Our goal was to **characterize the unique genetic repertory of uncultivated taxa**.

Vanni et al. focused on developing a methodology for unifying known and unknown protein families. They demonstrated how this strategy can reduce the number of unknowns in metagenomics datasets, and analyzed the diversity and lineage-specificity of functionally unknown protein clusters vs the known ones using metagenomic and genomic gene catalogs. Their main goal, as highlighted in their title and abstract, was therefore **to develop novel methods to unify the known and unknown sequence space**.

It is our understanding that the experimental design used in Vanni et al. was not intended to distinguish the unique genetic repertory of uncultured taxa, as they chose to separate unknown protein families based on the lack (or not) of a reference assembled genome, rather than on whether they come from fully sequenced lab-organisms, or from metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs). Consequently, almost all their analyses refer to global comparisons between protein families classified as Functional Known (K) and Functionally Unknown (U), further dividing the unknown category into two sub-categories:

- Genomic Unknowns (GU): protein families without functional annotation present in either fully sequenced genomes from cultured species, or Metagenome Assembled Genomes (MAGs) from uncultured organisms.
- And Environmental Unknowns (EU): protein families from environmental samples lacking a reference genome or MAG.

Note that the dataset analyzed in Rodríguez del Río et al. would be conceptually convoluted within the two unknown categories defined in Vanni et al. For instance, sequences from uncultured species will be present in the GU and EU categories, with no information on whether GU clusters are exclusive from uncultured species or not, which makes the comparison between both studies difficult at the biological level. To make results more comparable, data in Vanni et al. should be de-convoluted to identify uncultivated-only clusters, which is technically possible but was not intended in their analyses.

Moreover, Vanni et al. did not restrict their analyses to uncultured-only non-orphan protein clusters (i.e. no homologs beyond species level) that could be considered functionally relevant, as done in Rodríguez del Río et al. Note that the catalog reported in Rodríguez del Río et al., and all the derived results, are heavily biased towards protein families composed of full-length genes, spanning two or more species, without homologs in cultured species, under strong purifying selection, detected in 3 or more independent genomes, predicted or observed to be expressed, having a conserved sequence region of at least 20 contiguous amino acids, and predicted as an orthologous group without basal duplications at the bacterial or archeal level. *Therefore, we not only discarded all known protein families from our study, but also the majority of the unknown fraction (dropping ~97% of all inferred clusters).*

There are also technical decisions and scope differences that make results from both studies

hardly comparable. Most importantly, Rodríguez del Río et al. was based on more than 140,000 metagenome-assembled genomes, which allowed us to obtain reliable taxonomic predictions, inferring the functional genomic context of thousands of unknown protein families, and largely excluding incomplete genes from all the analyses. In Vanni et al. most data comes from environmental gene catalogs and it was enriched in incomplete genes, imposing important quality biases on the subsequent analyses.

3. High content of unknown protein families in uncultivated lineages.

Both studies report that the largest number of gene clusters with unknown function or novel protein families (hereafter referred to as unknowns) are found in uncultivated taxa. Rodríguez del Río et al. describe their findings in the section "High content of unknown protein families in the genomes of uncultivated taxa". Vanni et al. report the same observation, "the phyla with a larger number of MAGs are enriched in GCs of unknown function" and are mainly composed of "newly described phyla such as Cand. Riflebacteria and Cand. Patescibacteria (Anantharaman et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2015; Rinke et al., 2013), both with the largest unknown to known ratio" (Figure 5D, Supp. Note 14) and that "metagenome-assembled genomes are not only unveiling new regions of the microbial universe (42% of the reference genomes in GTDB_r86), but they are also enriching the tree of life with genes of unknown function". (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

We think Vanni et al. might have misinterpreted our results, as we never reached that conclusion in our work nor even tested it, as it was not necessary for addressing any of our questions.

Indeed, Vanni et al. showed that there is a larger proportion of unknown protein families in lineages with higher content of uncultivated taxa, a fact that has been reported not only in their paper but also in previous work (e.g., Overmann et al., 2017).

By contrast, the results shown in Figure 3A from Rodríguez del Río et al. indicate how many evolutionary conserved protein families (i.e. not orphan, under selection, etc.) are found, per genome, in different uncultivated lineages; allowing us to predict potential functional innovation hubs. In other words, we specifically identified lineages where individual species have a high number of evolutionary and functionally relevant genes per genome.

This is conceptually different from estimating the proportion of unknown to known protein families per lineage (as done in Vanni et al.). For instance, the Patescibacteria phylum, which was highlighted in Vanni et al. as the higher reservoir of unknown protein families, ranks 62nd in our analysis. This is so because we were targeting a different question, on a different dataset, and with a different metric.

We discussed the Patescibacteria phylum in our paper to just highlight that, despite their large genome reduction, these organisms still contain a relevant amount of unknown protein families from our subset catalog per genome, and that these conserved unknown protein families might indeed be tightly related to their particular biology.

In addition, it is worth noticing that, while our metrics were based on a heavily filtered set (see section 2 in this report), Vanni et reported their statistics based on a clustering dataset that: 1) might be over-split (i.e. not grouped by distant homology and cluster communities), 2) it is inflated by a high number of orphan genes (i.e. without homologs beyond species level) and 3) mixes protein families that are not necessarily unique from uncultivated lineages.

4. Predicting high-level synapomorphic traits

Both studies identify unknowns that are lineage-specific. Rodríguez del Río et al. identify "a core set of 980 protein family clusters synapomorphic for entire uncultivated lineages—that is, present in nearly all MAGs/SAGs from a given lineage (90% coverage) but never detected in other taxa (...) these newly discovered protein families can accurately distinguish 16 uncultivated phyla, 19 classes, and 90 orders, involving 179, 104, and 697 novel protein families, respectively". Vanni et al. provide more than 600K lineage-specific gene clusters of unknown function within the domain Bacteria (36 at the phylum level, 428 at the class level, and 1,641 at the order level (Supp. Table 10)) and Archaea (1 phylum, 25 classes, and 378 orders (Supp. Table 13-1)). (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

We think that in their letter, Vanni et al. are confronting data that are not comparable. We understand that a synapomorphic trait should represent an evolutionary novelty shared by all individuals of a taxon, differentiating it from other taxa (e.g., (Bern et al., 2006)). Therefore finding synapomorphic traits at high-level taxonomic ranks should be considered a rare event, and not all lineage-specific (LS) genes for a given clade are necessarily synapomorphic for the same group.

The data reported in Vanni et al. Supplementary tables 10 and 13 refer to the number of LS protein clusters found per rank, but not the synapomorphic ones (such a possibility was actually never discussed in their paper). Some examples of lineage-specific but not synapomorphic gene clusters can be easily found when inspecting the referred supplementary tables:

Cluster 33026695, with three sequences, is reported as Phylum specific in Supp Table 10 in Vanni et al. 2020, but could never represent a synapomorphic trait for the entire Firmicutes_G phylum:

```
GB_GCA_002408345.1 d_Bacteria;p_Firmicutes_G;c_UBA5301;o_UBA5301;f_UBA5301;g_UBA5301;s_ GB_GCA_001512545.1
d_Bacteria;p_Firmicutes_G;c_DTU065;o_DTU065;f_DTU065;g_DTU065;s_
GB_GCA_002399235.1 → d_Bacteria;p_Firmicutes_G;c_DTU065;o_DTU065;f_DTU065;g_UBA4881;s_
```

Or, Cluster 33278823, with three sequences, which is reported as LS for the bacteria domain in Supp Table 10 in Vanni et al. 2020, but could not be synapomorphic for the entire lineage:

```
GB_GCA_001778355.1 d_Bacteria;p_Firestonebacteria;c_D2-FULL-39-29;o_D2-FULL-39-29;f_D2-FULL-39-29;g_D2-FULL-39-29;s_
GB_GCA_001778375.1 d_Bacteria;p_Firestonebacteria;c_D2-FULL-39-29;o_D2-FULL-39-29;f_D2-FULL-39-29;g_D2-FULL-39-29;s_
GB_GCA_002839855.1 d_Bacteria;p_Goldbacteria-1;c_Goldbacteria-1;o_Goldbacteria-1;f_Goldbacteria-1;g_Goldbacteria-1;s_
```

While the last common ancestor rank of these clusters is at the reported phylum and domain levels, this is not enough to conclude that they are synapomorphic for the same clade. For instance, based on a quick screening of Vanni's et al. data using our methodology, we estimate that all the clusters reported in Supp tables 10 and 13 as specific at the domain level, 94% at phyla, and 45% at class, would be incorrect if interpreted as synapomorphic for the same taxonomic rank. In addition, and besides conceptual misinterpretations, there are numerous methodological choices in Vanni et al. that would compromise the prediction of synapomorphies out of their LS data.

First, Supplementary tables 10 and 13 in Vanni et al. report LS cases based on the same default set of clusters that they recognized to be potentially over-split (lines 202-206 and figure 2D in Vanni et al), which would have a direct impact on predicting synapomorphic traits. For instance, just by merging their clusters using distant homology detections (i.e. community clusters), and

restricting analyses to their high-quality cluster set, the LS numbers shown in the manuscript and the supplementary tables drop drastically.

Not to mention that Vanni et al. never intended to identify LS clusters that were unique from uncultivated taxa.

In our work, we considered that synapomorphic traits at high taxonomic levels are rare and should be predicted under stricter filters. Thus, we not only required putative synapomorphic families to be based on conserved full-length genes under strong purifying selection. We also imposed the conditions that protein families should be detected in at least 10 genomes from 10 different species (to avoid trivial cases), and that none of their members had a single remote homolog in other lineages (which would compromise our threshold of full specificity).

Given the serious concerns expressed in their letter, we took the effort of re-analysing all the protein clusters in Vanni et al. with our own approach and under the correct definition of a synapomorphic trait. Although we could not apply all our filters (e.g. dn/ds), we only identified 8 potential clusters in Vanni et al. data that would pass our predictive method. None of them were at the phylum level, and only 2 and 6 were found at class and order levels, respectively; and none of them overlapped with our synapomorphic predictions.

Finally, and probably most importantly, we fail to understand how a major result in our paper could overlap with findings that were not mentioned nor discussed in Vanni et al. Note that there is not a single sentence in Vanni et. el. where they discussed the value of any putative synapomorphic trait (or even LS cluster) found at high taxonomic ranks. Quite the contrary, authors only highlighted the high number of orphans found in their dataset (species-specific clusters).

5. Evolutionary significance

Both studies report that the unknowns could be considered relevant from an evolutionary perspective. Rodríguez del Río et al. provide a set of novel gene families that are phylogenetically conserved and under purifying selection, which parallels an observation that has been described in Vanni et al. based on phylogenetic conservatism of traits: "the unknown GCs are more phylogenetically conserved (GCs shared among members of deep clades) than the known (Fig. 5B, $p < 0.0001$), revealing the importance of the genome's uncharacterized fraction. However, the lineage-specific unknown GCs are less phylogenetically conserved (Fig. 5B) than the known, agreeing with the large number of lineage-specific GCs observed at Genus and Species level (Fig. 5A)." (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

Rodríguez del Río et al does not "*report that the unknowns could be considered relevant from an evolutionary perspective*", as we never intended to test if that statement holds true for the whole unknown sequence space.

What we did was predicting and discussing a small subset of protein families that, among all the unknowns, showed high evolutionary significance for specific uncultivated taxa. For this we selected uncultivated-only, non-orphans protein families under purifying selection; further delineating a smaller set of 980 families with greater evolutionary value, and establishing functional associations whenever possible. The only comparison that we performed was to show that synapomorphic families are indeed under stronger selection than other unknown and functionally relevant protein families, which reinforces their evolutionary value.

Vanni et al calculated phylogenetic conservation of all protein clusters using tauD (Martiny et al., 2013), a metric that calculates how dispersed a trait is in the underlying phylogeny. In figure 5B, Vanni et al. show that unknown protein clusters are, in general terms, more phylogenetically conserved than the known ones (a trend that they found to be inverted when looking at LS protein clusters).

We don't know how that could parallel our predictions. First, they never disentangled uncultivated-only families, so it is impossible to know if the same trend applies to our target data. Second, we never addressed the comparison between known and unknown protein clusters, as we actually discarded all known and most of the unknowns. Third, we used sequence conservation, purifying selection, and synapomorphic signal to delineate our predictions, which is a very different strategy compared to the phylogenetic conservation metric used in Vanni et al.

To illustrate this, we have now calculated tauD for our synapomorphic families (see next figure), finding that 1) tauD estimates do not correlate with the selective pressure on each family, and 2) the tauD values found for our predictions are about an order of magnitude larger than those detected in Vanni et al.

6. Ecological distribution

Both studies find unknowns that are widely distributed in the environment. Rodríguez del Río et al. report that "the majority of the new protein families (55%) are detected in more than ten samples, span at least two habitats", indicating a possible role as "core molecular functions from widespread microbial lineages, or derive from promiscuous mobile elements.". Similarly, Vanni et al. report the existence of a "pool of broadly distributed environmental unknowns", which "identified traces of potential ubiquitous organisms left uncharacterized by traditional approaches".

Furthermore, the results reported by Vanni et al. also support the findings observed by Coelho et al. [4] and mentioned by Rodríguez del Río et al. "This result contrasts with the habitat-specific pattern observed for the majority of individual species-level genes" where Vanni et al. also show the narrow ecological distribution of the unknown fraction reported in Figure 4D.

In addition, as shown by our colleagues in Holland-Moritz et al. [5] the majority of these dominant unknown genes are associated with mobile genetic elements in the soil. (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

Indeed, Vanni et al. found that the ecological dispersal of the unknowns is mostly narrow (as also found in (Coelho et al., 2022)) for the majority of protein clusters, as well as apparently dominated by mobile elements (Holland-Moritz et al).

This is exactly why we found our results novel and striking, as they inverted both patterns:

"Strikingly, we found that the majority of the new protein families (55%) are detected in more than ten samples, span at least two habitats, and are found in microbial communities with very different structures (average Bray-Curtis dissimilarity among samples containing each protein family is 0.88, Fig. S2).

(...) we found that protein families detected across different high-level taxonomic lineages (e.g., cross-domain and cross-phylum) are more likely to be part of mobile elements (Fig 3C). However, the vast majority of families (90.5%) appeared to be unrelated to obvious events of horizontal gene transfer, suggesting a more constitutive role in their host genomes." (Rodríguez del Río, et al. 2022)

This could indeed mean that we probably identified and characterized **a mixed and partial fraction** of the 'pool of broadly distributed EUs and GUs' whose existence was reported in Vanni et al., and we will be happy to mention this more explicitly in our paper. However, the fact that our predictions—which did not include ecological filters in the first place— invert the usual patterns of the unknown genes only reinforces the idea of being biologically relevant and validates our methodology to find functional and evolutionary significant unknown protein families.

7. Lineage specificity

"Both studies conclude that there is an increase in the number of lineage-specific unknowns towards the lower levels of taxonomy (i.e., genus, and species). Rodríguez del Río et al. report these results in Figure 3C and Vanni et al. in Figure 5A." (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

We think that Vanni et al. might have taken an anecdote in our data as a conclusion, ignoring the actual result in Rodríguez del Río et al. We actually use Figure 3C to report that, although there is an increase in the number of mobile elements towards the lower levels of taxonomy, the majority of our predictions do not seem to be the result of obvious transfer events:

" (...) we found that protein families detected across different high-level taxonomic lineages (e.g., cross-domain and cross-phylum) are more likely to be part of mobile elements (Fig 3C). However, the vast majority of families (90.5%) appeared to be unrelated to obvious events of horizontal gene transfer, suggesting a more constitutive role in their host genomes. " (Rodríguez del Río et al.)

The background data in figure 3C shows an increase in the number of LS families towards more specific levels of taxonomy, as generally expected, but we only used it to contextualize our actual results.

8. Methodological parallelisms

Both studies group the predicted genes into gene clusters using the clustering workflow of the software MMseqs2 [6] with a minimum identity threshold of 30%. (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

We actually used an approach that was originally published by us in Salazar et al., (2019), where we already addressed the idea of clustering sequences with similar domain architecture,

identifying confident clusters of unknown function, and unifying known and unknown metagenomics/genomics catalogs:

"We used BlastKOALA (Kanehisa et al., 2016) and eggNOG-mapper (Huerta-Cepas et al., 2017) to functionally annotate the OM-RGC.v2 according to orthologous groups in the KEGG database (release 86.1) and the eggNOG database (version 4.5.1), respectively. In total, 23.6% of the genes were annotated to a KEGG orthologous group (KO), and 60.9% were annotated to an eggNOG orthologous group (OG). In total, we annotated 9,026 KOs and 76,022 OGs. Genes that were not annotated to any OG were clustered de novo to define uncharacterized gene clusters (GCs). The clustering was performed with MMSEQS2 with the following options: -cluster-mode 2-cov-mode 1 -c 0.9 -s 7-kmer-per-seq 20. GCs supported by at least 10 sequences were kept (249,914 GCs in total). Thus, of the 39% of genes without known homologs in the eggNOG database, ~250,000 were grouped de novo by homology into high confidence (minimum cluster size = 10) gene clusters (GCs), accounting for 21.8% of all the genes in the OM-RGC.v2 (Figure 2)." (Salazar et al. 2019)

From our point of view, however, we consider these to be emerging standards and never judged the fact that Vanni et al. does not recognise Salazar et al. (2019) to be pioneer in using such an approach as a lack of recognition. Likewise, we don't understand why using MMSeqs-based clustering should be considered a relevant parallelism supporting a supposed omission of recognition to Vanni et al.

"Both studies detect and remove spurious genes searching the AntiFam [7] database. (...) Both studies use a multi-search approach with different sensitivity levels to confidently identify unknowns." (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

Rodríguez del Río et al. used AntiFam to locate spurious sequences and relaxed DIAMOND/BLAST searches to identify distant homologs, which is a generic procedure. We don't think this should be taken as a lack of recognition to Vanni et al.

"Both studies report a collection of small proteins of unknown function. In Rodríguez del Río et al. they report "13,456 families of proteins shorter than 50 residues, 486 of which have been reported previously as novel functional genes" in Sberro et al. (2019). Vanni et al. report a similar finding: "12,313 high-quality gene clusters [...] encoding for small proteins (<= 50 amino acids)", the majority of which are "unknown (66%), which agrees with recent findings on novel small proteins from metagenomes (Sberro et al., 2019)." (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

Rodríguez del Río et al. mapped their predictions to the most relevant catalog of unknown, but putatively functional, small peptides (Sberro et al., 2019); which is properly cited. We don't think this should be taken as a lack of recognition to Vanni et al. a lack of recognition to Vanni et al.

"Both studies search the unknowns against a database generated by Price et al. [8] using RB-TnSeq experiments. Rodríguez del Río et al. wrote "we mapped the protein family signatures derived from our catalog against the set of 11,779 unknown genes recently annotated based on genome-wide mutant fitness experiments, and found 69 matches to genes associated with specific growth conditions". Vanni et al. wrote, "We searched the 37,684 genes of unknown function associated with mutant phenotypes from Price et al. (2018) [...] to identify genes of unknown function that are important for fitness under certain experimental conditions". (Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary)

Rodríguez del Río et al mapped all their predictions to (Price et al., 2018)). to provide further hints on their putative functional roles. Vanni et al. used one example from Price et al. to showcase the use of genomic context for functional analyses. We don't know how our use of Price et al. could mean a lack of recognition for Vanni et al.

"Rodríguez del Río et al. identify "Synapomorphic protein families", "by calculating the clade specificity and coverage of each protein family across all GTDB v202 lineages". "Coverage was calculated as the number of genomes containing a specific protein family over the total number of genomes under the target clade. Specificity was estimated as the percentage of protein members within a family that belonged to the target clade. We considered protein families as synapomorphic if they contained at least 10 members (i.e., protein sequences from different genomes) and had a coverage higher than 0.9 and a specificity of 1.0 for a given lineage." Vanni et al. similarly identify a gene cluster as lineage-specific if present in less than half of all genomes and at least 2 with F1-score > 0.95 using the methods described in Mendler et al. [9], where the F1-score is calculated combining trait precision and sensitivity, where Precision indicates the degree to which a trait is conserved within a lineage, and sensitivity the exclusivity of that trait to a lineage." (*Fernandez-Guerra, biorxiv commentary*)

As shown in section 4, Rodríguez del Río et al. applied a different methodology both at the technical and conceptual level.

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